

THE MODELING OF UNI-DIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES INTERPHASE STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY: In the present work we have proposed the new method of the modelling of composites with interphases. The properties of the element of the structure, including fiber and interphases, were determined by the original strict analytical solution of the problem of the theory of elasticity. The problem of the stress-strain distribution of the elementary cell of composite was solved numerically with the determined effective elastic properties of the subsystem "fiber + interphases". It is very difficult to apply rather dense net for adequate covering the region of the thin interphase layer, using the numerical methods. The main advantage of the method presented is considering the interphase analytically. Treating the experimental data for glass- and carbo-composites with the help of the developed computer programmes we have extracted the effective properties of interphases for each composite. The last represents the most interest, as these parameters are unknown beforehand, while designing the composites.

KEYWORDS: interphase, micromechanics, analytical solution, numerical modelling, elastic properties, fractal structure.

INTRODUCTION

The main difficulty in the prediction of the properties of composites is to propose physically well grounded model of the structure of the material. It is very important to take into account the contribution of interphase into the total characteristics of the fibers-filled unidirectional composites. It is shown experimentally, that interphase is inhomogeneous [1], what is illustrated, for example, by microphotos of the carbo-plastic, obtained on electronic microscope (Fig.1).

However, the problem of stressed-strained state of all components of composite's structure and the problem of calculating macroscopic properties of the entire material are not solved yet. One of the main obstacles is taking into consideration the influence of interphase, which

thickness and properties are unknown beforehand. Besides, it is very difficult technically to take interphase into the numerical modelling of composite because of its small thickness.

Fig. 1: The microphotograph of carbo-plastic, obtained by electron microscope and the geometrical model of a cell of unidirectional composite with interphases.

In this work we report the new mathematical model for the determining of interphase properties for the definite pairs of fibers and matrixes. Our model includes the exact analytical solution of the problem of the definition of elastic constants for the structure's element "fiber + interphases", which essentially simplifies the consideration of interphase and the numerical modelling of the elementary cell of uni-directional composite, containing this element.

THE MODEL AND THE METHOD OF ANALYSIS

Analytical solution

We have considered the system (Fig.2), represented the cylinder with a set of co-axially arranged layers and displayed the cylindrical symmetry. The selected system simulates a fiber and interphases of unidirectional composite [2,3].

It was postulated, that each layer of a model was isotropic and its elastic properties and content by volume were known. We have named this cylinder as the compounded one (Fig. 1). This cylinder is equivalent to the cylindrically orthotropic homogeneous one, which has 9 elastic constants to determine.

Solving the problem of the theory of elasticity in displacements [4] for the compounded cylinder, it is necessary to determine stresses and displacements under various loads, that means to determine the response of a system to external loads. For the homogeneous orthotropic cylinder the inverse problem has been solved - we have determined the unknown elastic constants of the cylindrical orthotropic material - modules of elasticity E_i , ($i = r, \theta, z$) and Poisson's ratios μ_{ij} , ($i, j = r, \theta, z; i \neq j$) from the response of the system to the external loads.

Using the equilibrium equations in the cylindrical coordinate system, the Hooke's law $\{\sigma\}=[A]\{\epsilon\}$ and the Cauchy's relations [4] we have obtained the set of equations. The analysis was carried out in the following assumptions:

"R - compression"

$$\sigma_r(\mathbf{R}) = 0$$

$$\epsilon = 0$$

$$\mathbf{u}_r(\mathbf{R}) \equiv \mathbf{u}_1$$

$$\sigma_z \equiv \sigma_2$$

"Z - compression"

$$\sigma_z \equiv \sigma_4$$

$$\mathbf{u}_r(\mathbf{R}) = 0$$

$$\mathbf{u}_z = \epsilon_2 \mathbf{z}$$

"theta - compression"

$$\mathbf{u}_\theta = \gamma_2 r \theta$$

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{R}) = 0$$

$$\epsilon_z = 0$$

$$\sigma_z \equiv \sigma_6$$

"M - load"

$$\mathbf{M}_\theta \equiv \mathbf{M}$$

$$\epsilon_z = 0$$

$$\gamma$$

$$\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{u}_r(\mathbf{R}) \frac{1}{R}$$

Fig. 2: The schemes of loadings, used in analytical solution, where \mathbf{u} are the correspondent displacements, σ - the stresses, ϵ - the deformations, \mathbf{M} - applied moment.

- the problem is symmetrical about axis;
- the cylinder is endless;
- the cross-sections remain plane after deformation;
- the beams remain straight after deformation.

This assumptions gives the following set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{rr} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial r^2} + A_{r\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta}{r \partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) + \frac{1}{r} [(A_{rr} - A_{\theta r}) \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + (A_{r\theta} - A_{\theta\theta}) \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta}{r \partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) + (A_{zz} - A_{\theta z}) \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z}] = 0 \\
\frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} = 0 \\
\frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Solving the system of equations (1) we have received the following general solutions:
- for isotropic case:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_r &= Br + \frac{C}{r} + r \ln(r) \left(\frac{A_{rr} - A_{r\theta}}{2A_{rr}} \right) \\
u_\theta &= \gamma r \theta + \alpha r \\
u_z &= \varepsilon z + D
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

- for orthotropic case

$$\begin{aligned}
u_r &= Br \sqrt{\frac{A_{\theta\theta}}{A_{rr}}} + \frac{C}{r \sqrt{\frac{A_{\theta\theta}}{A_{rr}}}} + \frac{r(A_{zz} - A_{\theta z})\varepsilon}{A_{\theta\theta} - A_{rr}} + \frac{r(A_{r\theta} - A_{\theta\theta})\gamma}{A_{\theta\theta} - A_{rr}} \\
u_\theta &= \gamma r \theta + \alpha r \\
u_z &= \varepsilon z + D
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $B, C, \gamma, \alpha, \varepsilon, D$ - are the arbitrary constants for each case, A_{ij} - the coefficients of correspondent matrix of stiffness.

We have used all kinds of loadings, necessary to determine the coefficients of the matrix of stiffness (Fig. 2). The concrete forms of the fields of displacements for various loads were determined by satisfying the corresponding boundary conditions.

Let's examine one of the loads, for example "R-compression", in more detail. The stress $\sigma_r \equiv \sigma_I$ was applied to the lateral surface of the cylinder. "Prohibiting" a deformation in the direction of z ($\varepsilon = 0$), we have determined the displacement $u_r(\mathbf{R}) \equiv u_I$ and the stress $\sigma_z \equiv \sigma_2$ on the boundaries of the cylinder.

The case of the compounded cylinder with isotropic layers.

The necessary set of boundary conditions was obtained from the requirement of continuity of the fields of displacements and stresses for all cylindrical surfaces. Allowing for this, we have got the following boundary conditions:

- for two layers;

$$u_r^{(1)}(R_1) = u_r^{(2)}(R_1); \quad \sigma_r^{(1)}(R_1) = \sigma_r^{(2)}(R_1); \quad \sigma_r^{(2)}(R_2) = \sigma_I \tag{4}$$

- and for N layers ($2N-1$) equations:

$$u_r^{(i)}(R_i) = u_r^{(i+1)}(R_i); \quad \sigma_r^{(i)}(R_i) = \sigma_r^{(i+1)}(R_i); \quad \sigma_r^{(n)}(R_n) = \sigma_I \tag{5}$$

where N is the number of layers in the cylinder.

There are no displacements in the directions z and θ , for the considered load, therefore $\varepsilon = 0$ $\gamma = 0$. Then the fields of displacements take the following form [4]:

- for two layers:

$$u_r^{(1)} = B^{(1)}r; \quad u_r^{(2)} = B^{(2)}r + \frac{C^{(2)}}{r}; \quad u_\theta = 0; \quad u_z = 0 \quad (6)$$

- for N layers:

$$u_r^{(1)} = B^{(1)}r; \quad u_r^{(i)} = B^{(i)}r + \frac{C^{(i)}}{r}; \quad u_\theta = 0; \quad u_z = 0 \quad (7)$$

The quantity of unknown constants is $1 + 2(N-1) = 2N-1$, where N is the number of layers. Substituting the fields of displacements (6) in the boundary conditions (4) we have got the system of the linear equations, which allowed to determine all unknown constants $B^{(i)}$ and $C^{(i)}$, and then to find u_I and σ_2 .

The case of the homogeneous orthotropic cylinder.

Let's consider an effect of the load, treating a cylinder as homogeneous and orthotropic. The fields of displacements take the following form:

$$u_r = Br^s; \quad u_\theta = 0; \quad u_z = 0 \quad (8)$$

where $s = \sqrt{\frac{A_{\theta\theta}}{A_{rr}}}$ here and below.

Let's write the expression for the stress σ_r on the lateral surface of the cylinder:

$$\sigma_r(R) = A_{rr}BsR^{s-1} + A_{r\theta}BR^{s-1} = BR^{s-1}(A_{rr} + A_{r\theta}) = \frac{u_1}{R}(A_{rr}s + A_{r\theta}) = \sigma_I \quad (9)$$

hence

$$A_{rr}s + A_{r\theta} = \frac{\sigma_I R}{u_1} \quad (10)$$

and for σ_z on the surface of the end:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi R^2 \sigma_z &= \int_0^R 2\pi r dr (A_{zz}BsR^{s-1} + A_{z\theta}Br^{s-1}) = 2\pi \frac{u_1}{R^s} (sA_{zz} + A_{z\theta}) \int_0^R r^s dr = \\ &= 2\pi \frac{u_1}{R^s} (sA_{zz} + A_{z\theta}) \frac{R^{s+1}}{s+1} = \pi R^2 \sigma_2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

that gives:

$$\frac{sA_{zz} + A_{z\theta}}{s+1} = \frac{\sigma_2 R}{2u_1} \quad (12)$$

Thus, we have obtained two relations with unknown quantities A_{rr} , $A_{r\theta}$, $A_{\theta\theta}$, A_{rz} and $A_{z\theta}$ from the considered load for the orthotropic cylinder. The stress σ_I was set, and stress σ_2 and displacement u_I were determined, solving the problem for the compounded cylinder with isotropic layers.

In view of linearity of the basic equations of the theory of an elasticity, arbitrariness in the choice of σ_I has no influence to the right members of obtained equations for orthotropic cylinder, because the values σ_2 and u_I are, obviously, directly proportional to σ_I .

The next loads, shown on the Fig.3 were considered analogically to the case of «R-loading» and the analysis of it allowed us to receive four following equations:

$$A_{zz} - \frac{(A_{zz} - A_{z\theta})^2}{A_{rr}(s+1)^2} = \frac{\sigma_4}{\epsilon_2} \quad (13)$$

$$A_{z\theta} + \frac{(A_{r\theta} - A_{\theta\theta})(A_{z\theta} - A_{zz})}{A_{rr}(s+1)^2} = \frac{\sigma_6}{\gamma_2} \quad (14)$$

$$m \frac{R^2}{S+1} (S A_{r\theta} + A_{\theta\theta}) + \frac{\gamma R^2}{2} [A_{\theta\theta} - \frac{(A_{r\theta} - A_{\theta\theta})^2}{A_{rr} (S+1)^2}] = M \quad (15)$$

$$m (S A_{rr} + A_{r\theta}) + \gamma [A_{r\theta} - \frac{A_{r\theta} - A_{\theta\theta}}{S+1}] = 0 \quad (16)$$

Thus, we have received the system of 6 independent non-linear equations (10), (12), (13), (14), (15), (16) with six unknown constants - coefficients of the symmetrical stiffness matrix A_{ij} ($i, j = r, \theta, z$). The system supposes an analytical solution, which was obtained:

$$A_{rr} = - \frac{R^4 (m + \gamma)^2 \sigma_1^2}{2\gamma u_1^2 (M + \frac{m R^3 \sigma_1 (m + \gamma)}{\gamma u_1})} \quad (17)$$

$$A_{\theta\theta} = \frac{m^2}{(m + \gamma)^2} A_{rr} \quad (18)$$

$$A_{r\theta} = \frac{\sigma_1 R}{u_1} + \frac{m}{m + \gamma} A_{rr} \quad (19)$$

$$A_{zz} = \frac{\sigma_4}{\varepsilon_2} + \left(\frac{\frac{\sigma_2 R}{u_1} - \frac{\sigma_6}{\gamma}}{\sigma_1 R} \right)^2 \frac{\gamma^2}{(m + \gamma)^2} A_{rr} \quad (20)$$

$$A_{rz} = \left(\frac{\frac{\sigma_2 R}{u_1} - \frac{\sigma_6}{\gamma}}{\sigma_1 R} \right) A_{rr} + \frac{\sigma_2 R}{2u_1} \quad (21)$$

$$A_{\theta z} = \frac{\gamma m}{(m + \gamma)^2} \left(\frac{\frac{\sigma_2 R}{u_1} - \frac{\sigma_6}{\gamma}}{\sigma_1 R} \right) A_{rr} + \frac{\sigma_2 R}{2u_1} \quad (22)$$

Numerical Modeling of the Elementary Cell of Unidirectional Composite

The next step in our investigations was the numerical modeling of a rectangular cell of unidirectional composite, where we have used the properties of orthotropic cylindrical body, which modelled a fiber with interphases, obtained earlier. So, we have got the properties of the entire composite, taking into consideration the presence and the influence of interphase.

Fig. 3. The block diagram of the modeling.

We have developed the computer programme, using the method of finite differences, which allows to find the elastic properties of composites with different interphases, volume fraction of fibers and parameters of fibers and matrixes. The block diagram is presented on Fig. 3.

Now it is possible to find the properties of individual interphase. So, knowing the properties of the entire material from the experiment with the definite pair of fiber and matrix and the properties of the compounds separately, using the numerical methods we have found the properties of interphases for some composites.

We have analyzed glass-plastics with the different properties and thickness of the interphase. The experimental data, used in our calculations are shown at the Table 1. The results obtained by the computer simulation are presented on the Fig. 4 and the Fig. 5.

Table 1. The experimental data of composite compounds

The element of composite	Modulus of elasticity E , GPa	Poisson's ratio μ
Glass fiber	93	0.267
Epoxy-phenol matrix	3.3	0.35

Fig. 4. The dependence of the transverse elastic modulus on the thickness of interphase, $E_{int} = 10 \text{ GPa}$.

Fig. 5. The dependence of the longitudinal elastic modulus on the modulus of interphase, $l_{int} = 1 \mu$.

CONCLUSIONS

We have analytically determined the effective coefficients of the matrix of stiffness of inhomogeneous cylinder.

The main result of this research is making up the mathematical model and the computer programs to determine the interphase's parameters for various materials, which can be used for the prediction of the properties of unidirectional composites, considering the presence and influence of interphase layer. The results of the model calculations are in good agreement with the experimental data.

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